

Review Article

A Review on Current Antibiotic Resistance Trends of Uropathogens in India, A Survey from Urology Department 2020 – 2025

N. Vijay Vignesh A, Dr. Kurupatha Menatha Jayasree*, Sathyapriyan, G. Venkata Vignesh

Seven Hills College of Pharmacy, Tirupati, Andhra Pradesh

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 04 Feb 2026

Keywords:

E. coli ,Extended-spectrum β -lactamase , Klebsiella pneumoniae, Uropathogens, urosepsis

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.18479353

ABSTRACT

A urinary tract infection is a bacterial infection in any part of the urinary system. UTIs range from uncomplicated lower urinary tract infections to complicated infections-which include pyelonephritis and urosepsis-and catheter-associated UTIs. It affects all ages and sex, though distribution varies by population subgroup including venerable population, for example, pregnant women, paediatrics, elderly. AMR heightens the treatment failure rate, recurrence, hospital length of stay, cost, and mortality, especially when first-line agents fail and reserve drugs are necessitated. WHO and Lancet analyses have documented that globally, AMR in UTIs is a critical concern; in high-burden LMICs, India also depicts a high prevalence of resistant Gram-negative Uropathogens and considerable inter-regional variability. Empiric oral therapy for uncomplicated cystitis should favour nitrofurantoin or fosfomycin where local susceptibility supports this. Fluoroquinolones should be de-emphasized for empiric community UTI in many regions. Increase in CRKP increases dependence on combination/last-line agents in severe infection; provides additional support for stewardship, infection control, and routine molecular epidemiology in tertiary settings. We anticipate a further increase in the production of ESBLs, continued rise of carbapenem resistance in Enterobacterales, increase in fluoroquinolone resistance and significant regional variation all stressing the urgency for coordinated national efforts to support surveillance systems, promote antimicrobial stewardship, expand rapid diagnostic testing and reinforce infection control measures.

INTRODUCTION

A urinary tract infection is a bacterial infection in any part of the urinary system. UTIs range from

uncomplicated lower urinary tract infections to complicated infections-which include pyelonephritis and urosepsis-and catheter-associated UTIs. It affects all ages and sex, though

***Corresponding Author:** Dr. Kurupatha Menatha Jayasree

Address: Seven Hills College of Pharmacy, Tirupati, Andhra Pradesh.

Email ✉: kmjayasreemenon@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

distribution varies by population subgroup including venerable population, for example, pregnant women, paediatrics, elderly. (1) (2)

Most of the UTIs both community and hospital based are due to *Escherichia coli*; other common pathogens include *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Proteus* spp., *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Enterococcus faecalis*. The relative burden and antimicrobial susceptibility vary according to geography, hospital setting, patient comorbidity, and device use. (2) (3)

Mechanisms most relevant to Uropathogens include ESBL production (hydrolysing third-generation cephalosporins), carbapenemases (KPC, NDM, OXA-48-like enzymes), efflux pumps, porin loss, target modifications (quinolone resistance), and plasmid-mediated transmission of resistance genes. Molecular epidemiology has shown the rapid dissemination of plasmidborne carbapenemases, notably NDM variants, across the Indian subcontinent. (4) (5)

AMR heightens the treatment failure rate, recurrence, hospital length of stay, cost, and mortality, especially when first-line agents fail and reserve drugs are necessitated. WHO and Lancet analyses have documented that globally, AMR in UTIs is a critical concern; in high-burden LMICs, India also depicts a high prevalence of resistant Gram-negative Uropathogens and considerable inter-regional variability. (6) (7)

This review synthesizes data from 2020–2025, with an emphasis on Indian surveillance (ICMR-AMRSN, NCDC), peer-reviewed Indian multicentre studies, and international high-impact literature, to characterize trends, clinical impact, and responses, including stewardship, diagnostics, and therapeutic options.

METHODOLOGY OF LITERATURE REVIEW:

DATA SOURCES AND SEARCH STRATEGY:

We systematically searched PubMed/MEDLINE, Scopus, WHO-GLASS, ICMR AMRSN reports, and NCDC annual reports for studies and surveillance documents dated 2020–2025, using the keywords: “urinary tract infection India 2020,” “urine isolates India 2021–2024,” “ESBL India 2020–2024,” “carbapenem resistance India urinary,” and related MeSH terms. Grey literature from ICMR AMRSN and NCDC portals was included because of its central role in national surveillance. (5) (8)

INCLUSION AND EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

Included: Studies (retrospective/prospective, multicentre/single centre), surveillance reports, and review articles reporting microbiological isolates and their susceptibility data for urinary isolates in India (adults, paediatrics, pregnant women) between 2020 and 2025. Excluded: Small series (<20 isolates) without susceptibility data, non-peer-reviewed newspaper items, and studies without clear methodology.

TIME FRAME AND ANALYSIS:

Data were synthesised by pathogen and antibiotic class, noting year wise trends where available (ICMR reports and multicentre datasets). Where possible, we compare community vs. hospital and adult vs. paediatric/pregnant populations.

EPIDEMIOLOGY OF UROPATHOGENS IN INDIA (2020–2025):

PREVALENCE AND DISTRIBUTION:

Recent Indian datasets and nationwide antimicrobial resistance surveillance by ICMR-AMRSN have consistently identified *Escherichia coli* as the leading Uropathogens, contributing about 45–70% of all the isolates obtained. Following this is *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (8–20%), then *Pseudomonas* spp. (3–10%), followed by *Proteus* spp. and *Enterococcus* spp. Reports from several tertiary care centres across India also affirm the supremacy of *E. coli* both in community-acquired and hospital-associated urinary tract infections, underpinning its central role in the national epidemiology of UTI.(9) (10) (11)

TRENDS OVER THE LAST FIVE YEARS:

Longitudinal surveillance from 2020 to 2025 shows progressive increases in antimicrobial resistance among major uropathogens, particularly *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae*. There is growing resistance to fluoroquinolones and third-generation cephalosporins, with an increasing prevalence of extended-spectrum β -lactamase (ESBL) producers. Furthermore, resistance to carbapenem has emerged as a significant concern, especially among the isolates from hospital and ICU settings. These trends, documented year-on-year by the ICMR and National Centre for Disease Control, denote the dire need for revised empirical therapy guidelines and enhanced antimicrobial stewardship. (8) (9)

GEOGRAPHICAL DISPARITY ACROSS INDIA:

Multicentre studies have mostly illustrated significant regional heterogeneity in the prevalence of Uropathogens and their resistance patterns. The northern and northeastern regions of the country still show resistance to older antibiotics such as nitrofurantoin and fosfomicin. The metropolitan and southern regions display

elevated levels of fluoroquinolone and carbapenem resistance which primarily affects *Enterobacterales* bacteria. The different regions show these variations because they have distinct approaches to antibiotic usage and their infection prevention methods and monitoring systems. Continuous regional monitoring is therefore essential for indicating the locally appropriate therapy and formulating optimal empirical therapy. (10) (11)

ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE TRENDS (2020–2025):

Resistance Patterns Among Major Uropathogens:

Overall (2020-2025): Growing resistance among WHO-priority Gram-negative Uropathogens (particularly ESBL-producing *E. coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*) and growing carbapenem resistance in hospital isolates. Community urinary isolates still commonly remain susceptible to nitrofurantoin and fosfomicin, yet regional hot-spots demonstrate slowly increasing resistance. National surveillance reports alongside multiple regional studies confirm these trends. (12)

Escherichia coli:

- **2020–2021:** High and increasing rates of resistance to ampicillin (52.2%) and cotrimoxazole; fluoroquinolone (ciprofloxacin) resistance rose substantially across centres. ESBL (3rd-gen cephalosporin) production was already common in many hospital isolates.
- **2022–2023:** National AMRSN/NCDC reports show ciprofloxacin resistance frequently >30%, with many tertiary centres reporting 40–60% resistance in clinical urinary *E. coli* isolates; ESBL prevalence among *E. coli*

remained high (often 30–50% in hospital datasets). Nitrofurantoin and fosfomycin largely retained activity against uncomplicated community UTI isolates in many regions.

- **2024–2025:** Regional/tertiary-centre data and recent papers/news show continued high ciprofloxacin resistance across multiple centres reporting 50%+ in some series and a persistent ESBL burden. Some reports have demonstrated reduced susceptibility even to older oral options in hotspots. Treatment with nitrofurantoin/fosfomycin for uncomplicated lower UTI still generally reasonable but confirmation of local antibiogram is imperative.

Empiric oral therapy for uncomplicated cystitis should favour nitrofurantoin or fosfomycin where local susceptibility supports this. Fluoroquinolones should be de-emphasized for empiric community UTI in many regions. (5) (13) (14)

***Klebsiella pneumoniae*:**

- **2020–2021:** High ESBL rates; carbapenem resistance present but more concentrated in hospital/ICU isolates.
- **2022–2023:** ICMR/NCDC surveillance reports an increase in resistance to carbapenem by *Klebsiella* in nosocomial isolates; variation among centres—some tertiary centres report significant CRKP percentages.
- **2024–2025:** Several multicentre/regional reports and reviews indicate further increases in carbapenem non-susceptibility and more frequent detection of carbapenemase genes (NDM, OXA-48 variants) in clinical

Klebsiella isolates. Outbreak reports of CRKP in hospitals continue to be documented.

Implication: Increase in CRKP increases dependence on combination/last-line agents in severe infection; provides additional support for stewardship, infection control, and routine molecular epidemiology in tertiary settings. (15) (16)

***Enterococcus faecalis* / *Enterococci*:**

- **2020–2022:** Intrinsic resistance to cephalosporins expected. VRE historically low in some datasets but present.
- **2023–2025:** Surveillance and systematic reviews indicate increasing VRE prevalence over the decade, with intermittent institutional outbreaks reported in India and higher VRE rates in some hospitals. National surveillance still reports lower national proportions compared with Gram-negatives, but trend is upward.

Implication: For complicated UTIs/persistent bacteriuria with enterococci, susceptibility testing to vancomycin should be considered, which, in appropriate cases, may include linezolid and daptomycin; nosocomial spread of VRE must be prevented through infection control. (2)

***Proteus* spp.:**

- **2020–2023:** Usually susceptible to aminoglycosides and to many cephalosporins; resistance patterns variable, some areas report increasing ESBL among *Proteus* but in general less of a national focus than *E. coli*/*Klebsiella*.
- **2024–2025:** Limited multicentre series show mixed patterns — occasional increases in cephalosporin resistance where ESBLs are

common, but many isolates remain aminoglycoside-susceptible. Regional variability notable.

Implication: Select therapy based on local antibiogram; In many centres, Proteus remains relatively more treatable than CR-Enterobacterales. (17)

Pseudomonas aeruginosa:

- **2020–2022:** Marked heterogeneity — ICU and device-associated isolates often show high resistance to carbapenems and aminoglycosides; community urinary isolates usually less resistant.

- **2023–2025:** Continued alarmingly variable carbapenem resistance in hospitals; very high nonsusceptibility rates are reported in some tertiary ICUs while better aminoglycoside/colistin susceptibility is reported by other centres. Reports on difficult-to-treat strains and nosocomial outbreaks are alarming.

Implication: Pseudomonas UTIs (often complicated) require culture-directed therapy; empirical coverage for Pseudomonas should be restricted to patients with risk factors and guided by local ICU/hospital antibiograms. (18)

Table 1 : Antibiotic Resistance trends from 2020- 2025.

Pathogen	2020 (approx)	2021	2022	2023	2024–2025 (reported)
E. coli — ciprofloxacin resistance	~30%+ (many centres)	↑	↑ (30–50% common)	↑ (40–60% in many tertiary reports)	~40–60% in many centres; hotspots >60%.
E. coli — ESBL (3rd gen cep)	20–40% (varies)	↑	↑	30–50% (hospital datasets)	Remains high (30–50%+ in many hospital series).
Klebsiella — carbapenem resistance	Lower in community; present in hospitals	↑ (hospital isolates)	↑	Increasing reports of CRKP in tertiary centres	Substantial CRKP in many hospitals; molecular NDM/OXA detection increased.
Enterococcus — VRE	Low nationally (single-prevalence digit % in older data)	↑	↑	National reports and reviews: upward trend (institutional outbreaks)	Rising VRE clusters in hospitals; national % still lower than Gram-negatives but increasing.
Pseudomonas — carbapenem/ aminoglycoside	Variable; ICU higher	↑ in some centres	Highly variable	Very variable; many ICU series worrying	High variability — some ICUs very high carbapenem resistance; other centres lower.
Nitrofurantoin / Fosfomycin (oral)	Generally preserved for community UTI	Preserved in many community isolates	Preserved broadly	Preserved in many regions; some local decreases	Still commonly effective for uncomplicated community cystitis — verify local antibiogram

Table 2 : Extended-Spectrum β-Lactamase (ESBL) and Carbapenem Resistance:

Metric (what was measured)	≈2020 (baseline)	≈2025 (most recent syntheses / surveillance)	Change 2020 → 2025 (summary)	Notes / key sources
Overall— ESBL-producing	~15–25% (pooled, many settings) — high	~20–40% (pooled estimates vary by study & region; some meta-	Clear upward trend overall, but large regional	Representative syntheses and meta-analyses

Enterobacterales (clinical / carriage)	regional variation (some studies in 2018–2020 reported 15–30% or higher in hospitals/communities).	analyses reporting 25% community pooled, others reporting 40% in clinical isolates).	heterogeneity. Several meta-analyses and reviews 2023–2025 report higher pooled prevalences than earlier estimates.	2023–2025 (pooled ESBL carriage/infection estimates). (19)
Dominant ESBL enzymes	CTX-M family (CTX-M-15 common) already dominant by 2020.	CTX-M remains dominant globally (still expanding; plasmid spread persists).	No major change in dominant family (CTX-M), but wider environmental/community reservoirs detected.	Molecular surveillance & reviews (2020–2025). (20)
Clinical impact (resistance to 3rd-gen cephalosporins)	High — cephalosporin therapeutic failure increased; ESBLs limited options (carbapenems used more).	Still high; continued pressure on carbapenem use and increased co-resistance to fluoroquinolones/aminoglycosides.	Sustained clinical burden; contributed to more frequent use of broader agents.	Multiple reviews / meta-analyses 2021–2025. (21)
Overall prevalence — Carbapenem resistance (Enterobacterales, invasive isolates)	Varied by region. Example: EU/EEA population-weighted mean for invasive isolates ~10.4% (2019 baseline). Many countries had <5% while hotspots (South Asia, parts of LATAM) were higher.	Increasing in many regions. Example: EU/EEA population-weighted mean rose to ≈13.3% (2023); several countries/regions reported sharp rises and local hotspots with much higher percentages.	Clear increase in carbapenem resistance in many settings (esp. <i>K. pneumoniae</i>). Rise is uneven — worst increases in LMICs and some hospital networks.	ECDC (EU trends) and WHO/global syntheses; regional studies 2022–2025. (22)
Dominant carbapenemase types (enzyme landscape)	KPC, NDM, OXA-48-like were already established by 2020 — distribution was regionally distinct (KPC in parts of Americas/Europe; NDM in South Asia; OXA-48 in Europe/North Africa/Middle East).	Shift toward more mixed / co-producer strains (e.g., NDM + OXA-48 co-producers increasingly reported), continued spread of NDM into new regions, and persistent KPC in other locales.	Distribution evolved: spread + more co-producers (worse therapeutic implications).	Genomic/epidemiology reports 2022–2024; studies documenting NDM+OXA co-producers. (24)
Clinical burden / “nightmare bacteria” signals	Carbapenem-resistant infections were recognized as	Many countries reported large increases in CRE/NDM cases (e.g., CDC / national	Marked rise in “nightmare” CRE reports, esp. NDM; growing	CDC / national surveillance summaries and WHO 2023–2025

	high-mortality, relatively localized problem in many settings.	surveillance in 2019–2023 showed large increases in NDM cases in the US; WHO reported a sharp global rise through 2023).	community/hospital spread.	syntheses; major press coverage summarizing WHO findings. (25)
Treatment options / new drugs (access & resistance)	New β -lactam/ β -lactamase inhibitor combos (e.g., ceftazidime-avibactam, meropenem-vaborbactam) were available for KPC; options for MBLs (NDM) limited (aztreonam strategies, ceftiderocol experimental).	Newer options continued to be used, but reports of resistance to novel agents emerged; aztreonam + avibactam and ceftiderocol used for MBLs but availability/efficacy variable.	Armamentarium broadened but clinical utility limited by spread of enzymes (esp. MBLs) and emerging resistance; stewardship crucial.	Clinical reviews and treatment-focused papers 2020–2025. (26)
Surveillance & detection capacity	GLASS & national systems were expanding but coverage patchy (many LMICs under-reported).	Improved reporting & more molecular surveillance in many countries by 2023–2025 — led to better detection of trends (but gaps remain).	Apparent increase partly reflects real spread and partly improved detection/reporting.	WHO GLASS program & 2023–2025 reporting notes. (27)

Multidrug-Resistant (MDR), Extensively Drug-Resistant (XDR), and Pan-Drug-Resistant (PDR) Uropathogens

Definition and Clinical Importance:

MDR is defined as the resistance of an isolate to at least one antimicrobial agent in three or more antimicrobial categories. XDR strains are those that are non-susceptible to all but one or two antimicrobial categories, leaving clinicians with very limited therapeutic options. The most extreme end of the spectrum is represented by pan-drug-resistant (PDR) pathogens, which are non-susceptible to all available antimicrobial classes, including the last-resort drugs, leaving treatment virtually ineffective.

MDR, XDR, and PDR organisms that cause UTIs have also become a significant clinical and public health concern. These pathogens contribute to higher rates of treatment failure due to the scarcity of effective empiric therapies and are associated with increased morbidity, lengthened stays in hospitals, and greater healthcare utilisation—particularly in an ICU and catheter-associated environment. Management often requires the use of last-line agents such as colistin and tigecycline, which carry risks of nephrotoxicity and other side effects. The lack of reliable oral treatment options further complicates outpatient care and increases the risk of recurrence, pyelonephritis, sepsis, and urosepsis. Given the high burden of UTIs in India, the spread of MDR and XDR strains points to an imperative need for enhanced surveillance,

antimicrobial stewardship, and infection-control practices. (2)

Recent Indian Surveillance Data:

The consistent upward trend in MDR prevalence among uropathogens has been highlighted by the different Indian surveillance networks, including the ICMR-AMRSN and several other multicentre tertiary-care studies. The major urinary isolates like *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Acinetobacter baumannii* showed an increasing resistance pattern in many regions. Hospital and ICU isolates had very high rates of MDR, with prevalence rates as high as 50–70% in some centres among gram-negative Uropathogens.

The emergence of XDR clusters, including carbapenem-resistant Enterobacterales such as carbapenem-resistant *K. pneumoniae*, confers additional complexity to the therapeutic decisions. Though uncommon, PDR organisms have been recognized in high-risk units like ICUs and transplant wards and settings associated with long-term catheterisation. Clinicians are increasingly forced to consider last-line agents like colistin, polymyxin B, fosfomycin, and tigecycline despite their limitations in pharmacokinetics and toxicities. Overall, these trends suggest a transition from community-acquired, generally susceptible strains to hospital-driven reservoirs of extremely resistant MDR/XDR organisms. These call for continuous surveillance at the national level. (5) (18)

Hospital vs Community Isolates:

A clear difference exists between community-acquired versus hospital-acquired urinary isolates. Community strains-particularly *E. coli*-have traditionally exhibited lower rates of MDR, with many still susceptible to agents such as

nitrofurantoin, fosfomycin, and pivmecillinam. Community resistance is slowly rising, however, owing to factors such as irrational outpatient antibiotic consumption, over-the-counter availability of antibiotics, and non-compliance. In contrast, hospital and particularly ICU isolates exhibit much higher rates of MDR and XDR, especially among those who are catheterised or critically ill. This pattern is promoted by prolonged hospital stay, prior exposure to antibiotics, indwelling catheters, immunocompromised states, and biofilm formation related to various devices. Common hospital organisms include ESBL-producing Enterobacterales, carbapenem-resistant strains, and highly resistant *Pseudomonas* and *Acinetobacter* species. These differences have important implications for empirical therapy. While community-acquired UTIs can often be managed with narrower-spectrum oral antibiotics, hospital-acquired infections typically require broader empirical coverage informed by local antibiograms. Distinguishing between community and hospital onset is thus of utmost importance to avoid under-treatment and unnecessary broad-spectrum antibiotic use. (10) (13)

RISK FACTORS CONTRIBUTING TO RESISTANCE:

Empirical and Inappropriate Antibiotic Use:

High outpatient antibiotic consumption, especially excessive or inappropriate use of broad-spectrum agents such as fluoroquinolones and third-generation cephalosporins, significantly contributes to AMR in both the community and hospital settings. In many regions, antibiotics are initiated empirically without microbiological testing because of diagnostic uncertainty, lack of access to rapid culture facilities, or pressure to provide immediate symptom relief. Once initiated, therapy is often not adjusted ("no de-escalation") even after culture results become available,

thereby prolonging exposure to broad-spectrum agents.

Indeed, local prescribing patterns are repeatedly linked to resistance trends: fluoroquinolone use and fluoroquinolone-resistant *E. coli* are higher in those communities, while carbapenem use is associated with rising carbapenem-resistant *Enterobacteriales* (CRE) in hospitals. Additional contributing factors include the virtual lack of Antimicrobial Stewardship Programs (ASPs), grossly inadequate clinician training on rational prescribing, and time constraints in busy outpatient departments. Together, these practices create selective pressure driving the proliferation of MDR pathogens. (28) (29)

Self-Medication and OTC Sales:

Self-medication is prevalent in parts of India and other LMICs. The patients frequently buy antibiotics without prescription for symptoms such as fever, dysuria, or upper respiratory infections, which are often viral or self-limiting. Easy OTC availability, low cost, and perception of antibiotics as “quick cures” fuel this behaviour.

Incomplete or incorrect dosing means taking antibiotics for a period considered too short, using leftover tablets, or sharing medications. All these create subtherapeutic exposure, which accelerates the selection of resistance. While national regulations such as Schedule H1 attempt to restrict over-the-counter sales of critical antibiotics, the enforcement is not uniform. Variability in pharmacy oversight, economic dependency on antibiotic sales, and uneven state-level monitoring result in continued access in many areas without restriction. Consequently, self-medication remains one of the key yet preventable drivers of AMR. (30) (31)

Hospital-Acquired Infections and Catheter Use:

Healthcare settings, especially tertiary-care hospitals and ICUs, represent high-risk environments for the emergence and transmission of MDR organisms. An indwelling urinary catheter is one of the major risk factors for CAUTIs. The formation of biofilms on the surface of catheters protects bacteria from both antibiotics and the host immune responses, thus promoting resistance development.

Prolonged hospitalization, mechanical ventilation, immunosuppression, and invasive procedures further increase exposure to hospital-acquired pathogens such as ESBL-producing *E. coli*, *Klebsiella spp.*, and CRE. In particular, patients in the ICU are often exposed to multiple courses of broad-spectrum antibiotics, enhancing the selective pressure.

A catheter care bundle that includes sterile insertion techniques, daily review of the necessity of catheters and closed drainage systems, and early removal reduces rates of CAUTIs significantly. Hand hygiene adherence and robust infection prevention and control programs are required to disrupt the chain of transmission. (2)

Environmental and Socioeconomic Influences:

Environmental factors also play a critical role in the amplification and spread of AMR. Antibiotic residues from pharmaceutical manufacturing, hospital effluents, and agricultural runoff contaminate water bodies and soil, creating “hotspots” where resistant strains and resistance genes proliferate. Poor sanitation infrastructure facilitates fecal–oral transmission of resistant pathogens, particularly in densely populated urban settlements.

Socioeconomic disparities influence health-seeking behavior: a lack of access to trained practitioners means that communities rely on informal providers who often prescribe antibiotics inappropriately. Overcrowding, inadequate waste disposal, and irregular clean water supply further facilitate the spread of MDR organisms. With the interconnectedness of human, animal, and environmental health, a strategy toward controlling AMR should include integrated surveillance, policy, and intervention in the three domains. This encompasses enhancing wastewater management, regulation of antibiotic use in livestock, improving sanitation, and raising public awareness. (2) (30)

IMPACT ON CLINICAL OUTCOMES AND HEALTHCARE BURDEN:

Treatment Failures and Recurrence:

Antimicrobial resistance greatly reduces the efficacy of standard therapies for UTIs. In cases of failure of first-line empirical regimens—mostly because of ESBL-producing Enterobacterales or carbapenem-resistant strains—patients need to be escalated to second-line or parenteral antibiotics. This not only complicates the treatment but also delays clinical recovery and increases the risk of drug toxicities and nosocomial infections.

Recurrent UTIs are more common in the face of resistant pathogens. Persistent colonization, inadequate eradication of the organism, and the formation of biofilms contribute to multiple relapse episodes. These repeated infections create a cyclical burden leading to repeated antibiotic exposure, which further fuels the development and spread of resistance.

Adverse outcomes are disproportionately worse for certain populations. Pregnant women are at increased risk for pyelonephritis and adverse

maternal-foetal complications; paediatric patients may experience impaired growth and renal scarring; while elderly patients—particularly those with catheters or co-morbidities—have higher rates of bacteraemia and non-response to treatment. Overall, resistance changes what is generally an easily treatable infection into a persistent, often recurrent clinical problem. (32)

Duration Of Hospital Stay and Costs:

MDR UTIs directly translate to prolonged hospitalization and increased healthcare resource utilization. Patients infected with resistant pathogens often require admission for intravenous therapy, intensive monitoring, and additional diagnostic procedures. Higher rates of intensive care unit (ICU) transfer are observed, particularly when infections progress to complicated pyelonephritis or urosepsis.

The financial consequences are significant: increased direct medical costs through extended inpatient care, expensive broad-spectrum antibiotics, laboratory monitoring, and specialist consultations. The indirect costs of lost productivity, caregiver burden, and long-term complications further increase the societal impact.

Evidence from Indian cost-of-illness studies shows that MDR UTIs incur significantly higher per-patient costs than susceptible infections, a trend mirrored worldwide. These economic burdens not only stress tertiary care hospitals but also impact public health systems already struggling with high infectious disease loads. (6)

Data On Morbidity and Mortality:

The morbidity associated with resistant UTIs extends well beyond lower tract symptoms. As resistance limits effective antimicrobial therapy, the same infections tend to progress more readily

into severe forms such as acute pyelonephritis, emphysematous UTI, and urosepsis. These clinical conditions are linked to substantial organ dysfunction, such as acute kidney injury, septic shock, and multi-organ failure.

Mortality rates sharply rise in cases caused by MDR Gram-negative organisms, especially *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Global AMR burden estimates rank UTIs among the leading contributors to resistance-associated mortality, with Gram-negative pathogens responsible for a significant proportion of deaths. Of particular concern is the rising prevalence of carbapenem resistance, which leaves clinicians with limited and often toxic last-resort treatment options. Poor access to advanced diagnostics or timely care in low- and middle-income countries further elevates mortality risk. Thus, resistant UTIs are a critical public health threat, impacting morbidity, quality of life, and survival outcomes. (6) (2)

Current Guidelines and Stewardship Practices In India:

India's response to antimicrobial resistance is now anchored in a mix of national policy instruments, surveillance platforms, and hospital-level stewardship initiatives. The evolution from the first National Action Plan on AMR (2017–2021) to the recently launched NAP-AMR 2.0 has gradually strengthened the policy–practice continuum, with explicit links to state action plans, national surveillance networks (ICMR-AMRSN, NCDC), and hospital Antibiotic Stewardship Programmes (ASPs). (30) (33)

National Antimicrobial Resistance Action Plan (NAP-AMR) and Updates:

India's first National Action Plan on Antimicrobial Resistance (NAP-AMR 2017–2021) provided the

overarching policy framework for tackling AMR in line with the WHO Global Action Plan. It articulated six strategic priorities: improving awareness and understanding of AMR; strengthening knowledge and evidence through surveillance; reducing infection incidence via effective infection prevention and control (IPC); optimising antimicrobial use in human and animal health; promoting research and innovation; and ensuring strong leadership, intersectoral coordination and funding. (33) (34) (35) A key feature was its explicit One-Health orientation, linking human health, veterinary and food sectors, environment, and agriculture through a multi-stakeholder governance mechanism under the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare.

Operationalisation of the national plan has been driven through State Action Plans for Containment of Antimicrobial Resistance (SAPCARs). States such as Kerala (KARSAP), Madhya Pradesh (MP-SAPCAR) and Delhi (SAP-CARD) have developed their own AMR strategic plans and surveillance networks, which serve as sub-national platforms for stewardship interventions, statutory regulation (e.g. Schedule H1 enforcement), and integration of antibiogram data into clinical decision-making and essential drug lists. (36)(37) These state-level initiatives are particularly important for urinary tract infections, as they influence empirical prescribing norms in public hospitals and guide procurement policies for key UTI antibiotics.

Building on the experience and gaps identified during the first plan, the Government has now adopted NAP-AMR 2.0 (2025–2029). The second plan emphasises consolidation and scale-up rather than de-novo pilot initiatives: expanding functional microbiology and AMR surveillance capacity beyond tertiary centres to district and sub-district hospitals; strengthening ASPs and IPC

programmes; standardising methodologies for knowledge, attitude and practice (KAP) assessments; and improving data sharing between human, animal and environmental sectors. For common community infections like UTIs, NAP-AMR 2.0 underlines rational outpatient prescribing, restricted OTC antibiotic sales, and wider dissemination of context-specific treatment guidelines as key levers to curb resistance. (30)(38)(39)

Hospital Antibiotic Stewardship Programmes (ASPs):

At the hospital level, Antibiotic Stewardship Programmes (ASPs) have emerged as the principal implementation arm of national AMR policy. Many tertiary-care hospitals, especially those that are part of the ICMR Antimicrobial Resistance Surveillance and Research Network (AMRSN) or the National AMR surveillance network coordinated by NCDC, have established formal ASPs. These typically involve multidisciplinary teams comprising microbiologists, infectious disease physicians (where available), clinical pharmacists, nursing staff and hospital administrators. Their core activities include development of hospital-specific antibiotic policies informed by local antibiograms, formulary restriction and pre-authorisation for reserve drugs (e.g. carbapenems, colistin), prospective audit and feedback on prescriptions, dose optimisation including renal dose adjustments, IV-to-oral switch policies, and regular clinician education.

Nevertheless, ASP coverage and intensity remain highly variable across the country. Many secondary-level and smaller private hospitals lack on-site microbiology laboratories, infectious disease specialists, or clinical pharmacists, resulting in empirical and often broad-spectrum antibiotic use for UTIs without reference to local

resistance data. Resource constraints, competing clinical workloads, limited electronic health record systems, and inadequate administrative prioritisation further hinder systematic stewardship implementation. Recognising these gaps, ICMR has initiated efforts to extend ASP and infection prevention and control (IPC) interventions to secondary-care settings through hub-and-spoke models, capacity-building initiatives, and targeted calls for implementation research. In the context of urology and nephrology services, ASPs that integrate catheter-associated UTI (CAUTI) bundles, stringent indications for urine cultures, and step-down or de-escalation guided by culture reports are particularly critical to reducing the selection pressure that drives MDR Uropathogens.(9) (40)

Rational prescribing and surveillance networks (ICMR-AMRSN, NCDC):

Rational antibiotic prescribing in India is increasingly being supported by robust national surveillance platforms. The ICMR-AMRSN, initiated in 2013, now includes a network of tertiary-care hospitals generating standardised data on resistance trends in priority pathogens from key specimen types, including urine. Annual AMRSN reports and hospital antibiograms derived from this network are used to update empirical treatment recommendations, inform national and institutional antibiotic policies, and identify “hot-spot” organisms such as ESBL-producing Enterobacterales and carbapenem-resistant Gram-negative bacilli that complicate UTI management.

In parallel, the National Centre for Disease Control (NCDC) coordinates the National Programme on AMR Containment and serves as India’s national coordinating centre for the WHO Global Antimicrobial Resistance Surveillance System (GLASS). India enrolled in GLASS in 2017–2018, and since then NCDC has been compiling and

uploading national AMR data—largely derived from a sentinel network of public sector laboratories—onto the GLASS platform each year. These surveillance systems use tools such as WHONET for data management and incorporate external quality assurance mechanisms, thereby enhancing the reliability and comparability of resistance data across regions.

Together, ICMR-AMRSN and the NCDC-led national network provide the empirical foundation for data-driven prescribing in UTIs. Their outputs support the revision of standard treatment guidelines, state and hospital-level antibiotic policies, and essential medicines lists, while also feeding into global assessments of AMR burden and trends. For clinicians, access to regularly updated antibiograms allows more nuanced empirical choices (for example, avoiding fluoroquinolones or third-generation cephalosporins in regions with high resistance and preferring nitrofurantoin or fosfomycin for uncomplicated cystitis where susceptibility remains preserved), thereby aligning individual patient care with national stewardship priorities. (8) (9)

Emerging Therapeutic Options and Preventive Strategies:

Newer antimicrobials and combination therapies:

Novel combinations of BL/BLI and optimized aminoglycoside regimens have expanded the therapeutic options against MDR Gram-negative uropathogens, especially ESBL- and certain carbapenemase-producing strains. Agents such as ceftazidime–avibactam, ceftolozane–tazobactam, and meropenem–vaborbactam show improved activity against resistant *Enterobacterales* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* due to the inhibition of key β -lactamases and restoration of the activity of

the partner β -lactams. In turn, novel dosing strategies for aminoglycosides (for example, extended-interval or once-daily high-dose regimen driven by pharmacokinetic/pharmacodynamic considerations) maximize bacterial kill while limiting nephrotoxicity, particularly when used as part of combination regimens.

Combination therapies, such as a carbapenem plus an aminoglycoside or a BL/BLI plus colistin or fosfomycin, are often used in severe infections caused by XDR or carbapenem-resistant organisms, with a view to achieving synergy and preventing further emergence of resistance. However, the high cost of these newer molecules and limited availability outside tertiary centers, coupled with the need for stewardship, severely restrict their widespread use in low- and middle-income settings like India. (41)

Phage Therapy and Non-Antibiotic Approaches:

Phage therapy has re-emerged as a possible adjuvant or alternative to antibiotics for MDR urinary pathogens. Bacteriophages are viruses that infect only bacteria and can be prepared either as single phage's or cocktails acting on Uropathogens like MDR *E. coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Their ability to lyse bacteria, including those embedded in biofilms on catheters or in the uroepithelium, makes them appealing for complicated and recurrent UTIs where conventional agents fail. Early-phase clinical experiences and case series have been described, many published via platforms such as ScienceDirect, indicating clinical benefit in selected, but often compassionate-use, scenarios, though standardized dosing, regulatory pathways, and large randomized trials remain highly lacking.

Parallel to this, bacteriocins and AMPs are being explored as novel non-traditional antibacterials.

These bacteria-derived or synthetically engineered molecules interfere with bacterial cell membrane integrity, inhibit cell wall synthesis, or modulate host immune response. Their broad mechanistic diversity and lower cross-resistance with conventional antibiotics raise their potential against MDR uropathogens. However, instability in biological fluids, toxicity, delivery of active compounds into the urinary tract, and high cost of production remain key translational challenges. These novel non-antibiotic strategies presently represent promising but largely investigational adjuncts rather than established standard therapy. (42)

Probiotics, vaccines, and preventive measures:

Modulation of genitourinary and gut microbiota using probiotics is a potentially complementary preventive strategy against recurrent UTIs, especially in women. Probiotic preparations that include *Lactobacillus* strains aim at reconstituting protective vaginal and intestinal flora, thereby reducing the uropathogenic *E. coli* colonization and risk of ascending infection. Several clinical trials have reported reductions in recurrence, but heterogeneity in strains, formulations, and designs means that these studies are not yet definitive and standardized recommendations are still evolving. Vaccine approaches, such as oral immunostimulants derived from bacterial lysates of uropathogenic *E. coli* and parenteral vaccines tested in experimental settings, targeting key virulence factors of *E. coli*, have shown promise in reducing recurrence rates but need large, good-quality randomized, controlled trials to definitively establish efficacy, optimal schedules, and long-term safety.

While these biologic strategies continue to evolve, timely and inexpensive prevention interventions are necessary. Stringent catheter care bundles—aseptic insertion, closed drainage systems,

maintenance protocols, and prompt removal of unnecessary catheters—are critical in preventing catheter-associated UTIs and the selection of MDR organisms. Hand hygiene promotion, adequate hydration, appropriate perineal hygiene, and avoidance of unnecessary antibiotic prescriptions are paramount in hospital and community settings. Public and patient education is critical in this respect through the emphasis on the risks of self-prescribing of antibiotics, incomplete antibiotic courses, and over-the-counter antibiotic use, both to reduce the incidences of infection and slow the emergence of resistance, especially in high-burden countries. (2)

Role of rapid diagnostics in resistance control:

RDTs for pathogen identification and AST are the key to better management of MDR UTIs. Standard culture-based techniques require 24 to 72 hours, a time in which patients are commonly treated empirically with broad-spectrum agents. New technologies, from automated microfluidic AST platforms to nucleic-acid amplification tests, MALDI-TOF mass spectrometry-based identification, and multiplex PCR panels, can significantly shorten turnaround times. A few point-of-care systems have the ability to yield organism identification along with targeted susceptibility information in about 45 to 60 minutes, thus allowing clinicians to tailor therapy much earlier in illness. By reducing diagnostic uncertainty, rapid tests can reduce inappropriate empirical therapy, promote early de-escalation from broad-spectrum to narrow-spectrum agents, and identify those patients for whom non-antibiotic management is appropriate. At a population level, this can lead to less selection pressure for resistance and more rational use of antibiotics. However, high upfront costs, the need for laboratory infrastructure and trained personnel, integration with electronic prescribing systems,

and reimbursement issues all limit widespread implementation, particularly in resource-constrained settings. Building laboratory capacity, integrating rapid diagnostics into antimicrobial stewardship programs, and ensuring contextually appropriate adoption will be important for maximizing the role these technologies can play in combating MDR Uropathogens. (43)

Challenges and Future Perspectives:

Gaps In Surveillance and Data Integration:

Surveillance for antimicrobial resistance in India is still fragmented, with marked geographic inequities, limited representation from the private sector (where a large proportion of care is delivered), and considerable variability in laboratory capacity and quality. Many microbiology laboratories do not consistently follow standardized operating procedures, susceptibility testing guidelines, or external quality assurance schemes, which undermines comparability of data across sites. In addition, microbiological findings are rarely linked with granular clinical information such as comorbidities, prior antibiotic exposure, treatment regimens, and outcomes, making it difficult to generate actionable evidence for guideline development and impact evaluation. These weaknesses delay recognition of emerging resistance patterns and limit timely, data-driven policy responses. Consolidating and expanding the ICMR-AMRSN network, investing in interoperable national data repositories, and strengthening India's contribution to global platforms such as GLASS are therefore critical steps toward a more responsive, integrated AMR surveillance ecosystem. (5) (8)

Need For Policy Strengthening and Public Awareness:

Despite the existence of regulatory frameworks, enforcement remains inconsistent, particularly with respect to over-the-counter sales of antibiotics, informal prescribing, and inadequate documentation of antimicrobial use. Stronger policy implementation must be accompanied by sustained investment in hospital- and community-based antimicrobial stewardship programs, including staffing, decision-support tools, audit-and-feedback mechanisms, and access to diagnostics. At the population level, large-scale, culturally tailored public awareness campaigns are needed to address widespread practices such as self-medication, sharing of leftover antibiotics, and premature discontinuation of therapy, which collectively accelerate resistance. Experiences from state-level SAPCAR initiatives demonstrate that coordinated, multisectoral models—combining regulation, capacity building, and behavior-change communication—can be scaled and adapted across diverse health system settings in India. (30)

Research Priorities for The Next Decade:

Over the coming decade, research on AMR in India must prioritize robust regional surveillance platforms that systematically integrate microbiological data with clinical, pharmacological, and outcome indicators, enabling more precise risk stratification and context-appropriate empiric therapy. There is a pressing need for pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic studies of key antimicrobials in Indian populations, including vulnerable groups, to optimize dosing and reduce toxicity while preserving efficacy. Clinical trials and implementation studies evaluating non-antibiotic preventive strategies—such as vaccines, bacteriophage therapy, probiotics, and infection-prevention bundles—are equally important, particularly in high-burden settings. In parallel,

implementation research should focus on designing, testing, and scaling antibiotic stewardship interventions that are feasible in low-resource hospitals and primary care facilities. Finally, systematic environmental surveillance for antibiotic residues, resistance genes, and resistant organisms in water, soil, and effluents is essential to fully operationalize a One Health approach and inform regulatory action on pharmaceutical and agricultural waste. (2) (40)

CONCLUSION:

We anticipate a further increase in the production of ESBLs, continued rise of carbapenem resistance in Enterobacterales, increase in fluoroquinolone resistance and significant regional variation all stressing the urgency for coordinated national efforts to support surveillance systems, promote antimicrobial stewardship, expand rapid diagnostic testing and reinforce infection control measures. Practitioners will need to depend on pertinent local antibiograms and stewardship principles in order to direct empirical therapy, and those in leadership positions should prioritize One-Health initiatives and the promotion of new anti-infective therapeutics which confront this rapidly advancing resistance challenge.

REFERENCES

1. He, Y., Zhao, J., Wang, L. et al. Epidemiological trends and predictions of urinary tract infections in the global burden of disease study 2021. *Sci Rep* 15, 4702 (2025).
2. Li X, Fan H, Zi H, Hu H, Li B, Huang J, Luo P, Zeng X. Global and Regional Burden of Bacterial Antimicrobial Resistance in Urinary Tract Infections in 2019. *J Clin Med*. 2022 May 17;11(10):2817.
3. Jahan F, Anwer M. 2025. Nature of antimicrobial resistance of pathogens causing urinary tract infection in Bangladesh: age and gender profiles. *Microbiol Spectr* 13:e02287-24.
4. Ho CS, Wong CTH, Aung TT, Lakshminarayanan R, Mehta JS, Rauz S, et al. Antimicrobial resistance: a concise update. *Lancet Microbe*. 2024 July.
5. Indian Council of Medical Research. Annual Report 2023-24. New Delhi: Indian Council of Medical Research; 2024
6. Global burden of bacterial antimicrobial resistance in 2019: a systematic analysis, Murray, Christopher J L et al. *The Lancet*, Volume 399, Issue 10325, 629 – 655.
7. World Health Organization. Antimicrobial resistance. Geneva: WHO; 21 November 2023
8. National Centre for Disease Control. Annual Report 2023 (January–December). New Delhi: National Centre for Disease Control; 2024.
9. Indian Council of Medical Research. Reports. New Delhi: ICMR.
10. Vyas A, Karuna T, Kumar S, Gupta A, Sampath A, et al. (2023) Antimicrobial Resistance Trends in Urinary Tract Infection at Secondary Care Centres in Central India: Carbapenem Resistance Crossing 20% in Community. *Infect Dis Diag Treat* 7: 235.
11. Rizvi M, Malhotra S, Sami H, Agarwal J, Siddiqui AH, Devi S, et al. *Klebsiella pneumoniae* urinary tract infection: A multicentric study highlights significant regional variations in antimicrobial susceptibility across India.
12. Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR)-Antimicrobial Resistance Surveillance Network. Annual Report 2021: Antimicrobial Resistance Research & Surveillance Network. New Delhi: ICMR; 2021.
13. Jennifer H Ku, Katia J Bruxvoort, S Bianca Salas, Cara D Varley, Joan A Casey, Eva Raphael, Sarah C Robinson, Keeve E

- Nachman, Bruno J Lewin, Richard Contreras, Rong X Wei, Magdalena E Pomichowski, Harpreet S Takhar, Sara Y Tartof, Multidrug Resistance of *Escherichia coli* From Outpatient Uncomplicated Urinary Tract Infections in a Large United States Integrated Healthcare Organization, *Open Forum Infectious Diseases*, Volume 10, Issue 7, July 2023, ofad287,
14. Nkontcho Djamkeba F, Sainte-Rose V, Lontsi Ngoulla GR, Roujansky A, Abboud P, Walter G, Houcke S, Demar M, Kallel H, Pujo JM, Djossou F. Trends in the Prevalence of Antimicrobial Resistance in *Escherichia coli* Isolated from Outpatient Urine Cultures in French Amazonia. *Am J Trop Med Hyg.* 2024 Jun 25;111(2):287-296.
 15. Rizvi M, Malhotra S, Sami H, Agarwal J, Siddiqui AH, Devi S, Poojary A, Thakuria B, Princess I, Gupta A, Al Malehi A, Sultan A, Jitendranath A, Mohan B, Khan F, El Tahir H, Ilanchezhyan N, Jain M, Khan M, Singh NP, Taneja N. *Klebsiella pneumoniae* urinary tract infection: A multicentric study highlights significant regional variations in antimicrobial susceptibility across India. *Int J Regul Sci.* 2025;100605.
 16. El Aila, N.A., El Aish, K.I.A. Six-year antimicrobial resistance patterns of *Escherichia coli* isolates from different hospitals in Gaza, Palestine. *BMC Microbiol* 25, 559 (2025).
 17. Ahirwar, N.; Singha, T.K.; Srivastava, M.; Pal, M. Epidemiological Study of the Antimicrobial Resistance Pattern of a Suspected Urinary Tract Infection in a Super Surgical, Super Specialty Hospital in Northern India. *Med. Sci. Forum* 2024, 24, 16.
 18. Sharma P, Sarwat T, Mahajan S, K Kakru D, Kaushik N. Burden of Carbapenem Resistant Urinary Isolates of *E. coli* and *Klebsiella* at Tertiary Care Hospital. *J Neonatal Surg* . 2025Jul.10 ;14(32S):4691-8.
 19. Rita W Y Ng, Liuyue Yang, Sai Hung Lau, Peter Hawkey, Margaret Ip, Global prevalence of human intestinal carriage of ESBL-producing *E. coli* during and after the COVID-19 pandemic, *JAC-Antimicrobial Resistance*, Volume 7, Issue 1, February 2025.
 20. Girlich D, Bonnin RA, Naas T. Occurrence and diversity of CTX-M-producing *Escherichia coli* from the Seine River. *Front Microbiol.* 2020;11:603578.
 21. Arias Ramos D, Moreno Henao LE, Bolaños OF, Roa Martínez ÁJ. ESBL-producing Enterobacteriaceae, an unnoticed pandemic with challenges in clinical practice, a mini-review. *J Infect Epidemiol.* 2024 Dec 24;3:1178.
 22. European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control. Carbapenem-resistant Enterobacterales – third update, 3 February 2025. Stockholm: ECDC; 2025. Report No.: TQ-01-25-005-EN-N.
 23. Lazar, D.S.; Nica, M.; Dascalu, A.; Oprisan, C.; Albu, O.; Codreanu, D.R.; Kosa, A.G.; Popescu, C.P.; Florescu, S.A. Carbapenem-Resistant NDM and OXA-48-like Producing *K. pneumoniae*: From Menacing Superbug to a Mundane Bacteria; A Retrospective Study in a Romanian Tertiary Hospital. *Antibiotics* 2024, 13, 435.
 24. Stobbe M. ‘Nightmare bacteria’ cases are increasing in the U.S. Associated Press. 2025 Sep 23.
 25. Appalaraju B, Rizwana MM, Shanmugapriya S, Kumar JV. Common Genotypes of Carbapenamase Observed in Members of the Enterobacteriaceae in Tertiary Care Hospital in South India. *J Pure Appl Microbiol.* 2025;19(2):1124-1133.
 26. World Health Organization. Global Antimicrobial Resistance and Use

- Surveillance System (GLASS) . Geneva: WHO.
27. Ahmed SK, Hussein S, Qurbani K, Ibrahim RH, Fareeq A, Mahmood KA, Mohamed MG. Antimicrobial resistance: Impacts, challenges, and future prospects. *Glob Health Med.* 2024;100081.
 28. Dynamic association of antimicrobial resistance in urinary isolates of *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* between primary care and hospital settings in the Netherlands (2008–2020): a population-based study. Martínez, Evelyn PamelaCohen Stuart, James W.T. et al. *The Lancet Regional Health – Europe*, Volume 50, 101197
 29. Press Information Bureau. Ministry of Health and Family Welfare. PIB; 06 AUG 2024.
 30. National Action Plan on containment of Antimicrobial Resistance (NAP-AMR)” — Press Release (3 Feb 2023) — mentions that antibiotics under Schedule H1 can only be sold by retail on prescription.
 31. McCowan, C., Bakhshi, A., McConnachie, A. et al. *E. coli* bacteraemia and antimicrobial resistance following antimicrobial prescribing for urinary tract infection in the community. *BMC Infect Dis* 22, 805 (2022).
 32. WHO Team. India: National Action Plan on Antimicrobial Resistance (NAP-AMR) 2017–2021. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2017 Apr [cited 2025 Nov 20]. 57 p
 33. National Medical Commission. AMR Module for Prescribers. New Delhi: National Medical Commission; 2024 Jun [cited 2025 Nov 20].
 34. Nair M, Zeegers MP, Varghese GM, Burza S. India’s National Action Plan on Antimicrobial Resistance: a critical perspective. *J Glob Antimicrob Resist.* 2021;27:236–238.
 35. National Centre for Disease Control, Ministry of Health & Family Welfare. National action plan on AMR (NAP-AMR) . New Delhi: Government of India; [cited 2025 Nov 20]
 36. The Times of India. State bolsters antimicrobial resistance surveillance. *Times of India* . 2025 Nov 11 [cited 2025 Nov 20].
 37. Sinha R. WAAW 2025: India’s much awaited second version of the National Action Plan on AMR released. *Down To Earth* . 2025 Nov 18 [cited 2025 Nov 20]
 38. ETHealthWorld. Nadda launches National Action Plan on AMR. *ETHealthWorld* . 2025 Nov 18 [cited 2025 Nov 20].
 39. Indian Council of Medical Research. AMRSN (Antimicrobial Resistance Surveillance & Research Network) . New Delhi: ICMR; [cited 2025 Nov 20].
 40. Ho CS, Wong CTH, Aung TT, Lakshminarayanan R, Mehta JS, Rauz S, McNally A, Kintses B, Peacock SJ, de la Fuente-Nunez C, Hancock REW, Ting DSJ. Antimicrobial resistance: a concise update. *Lancet Microbe.* 2024;6(1):100947.
 41. Ahmed SK, Hussein S, Qurbani K, Ibrahim RH, Fareeq A, Mahmood KA, Mohamed MG. Antimicrobial resistance: Impacts, challenges, and future prospects. *J Med Surg Public Health.* 2024;2:100081.
 42. The Guardian. Rapid UTI test that cuts detection time to 45 minutes awarded Longitude prize. *The Guardian* . 2024 Jun 12 [cited 2025 Nov 20].

HOW TO CITE: N. Vijay Vignesh A, Dr. Kurupatha Menatha Jayasree, Sathyapriyan, G. Venkata Vignesh, A Review on Current Antibiotic Resistance Trends of Uropathogens in India, A Survey from Urology Department 2020 – 2025, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, Vol 4, Issue 2, 449-466. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18479353>

